

BRIDGING THE GAP: ALIGNING ARCHITECTURAL EDUCATION IN SAUDI ARABIA WITH LABOUR MARKET DEMANDS AND INTERNATIONAL ACCREDITATION STANDARDS

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Abstract

An investigation has been made to predict the effects of forebody and afterbody as one of the pivotal initiatives of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030; the human capabilities development program is a beacon of hope, aiming to enhance the skills of citizens and boost global competitiveness. As a critical project under this initiative, the Ministry of Education has been diligently updating educational programs to meet the needs of the global job market. In line with these efforts, this study investigates the alignment of architectural education in Saudi Arabia with labour market demands and international accreditation requirements. Using curricula of fourteen local architectural programs and Junior Jobs required skills and knowledge from International Architectural Firms. The study achieves its objectives through a comprehensive survey of local educational institutes, tabulating their curriculums, and identifying the main topics, categories, and sections of these curriculums. The study then compares the curricula to international accreditation requirements and market-required skills and knowledge. Results highlight gaps, including business practice background knowledge, problem-solving skills, analytical skills, experience with modern construction materials and techniques, and advanced knowledge of computer tools. Finally, specific fields to be enhanced within the curricula to increase the readiness of the graduates were introduced. Moreover, the study recommended cooperation actions between the three directing parties of the education process: professional associations, educational institutions, and accrediting organizations.

Keywords: Accreditation, Architecture, Curriculum, Professional practice.

1. Introduction

Humans are the main focus of the Saudi Vision 2030. One of its objectives is to prepare graduates to compete in a global work environment. Saudi Arabia is considered the leading construction market in the MENA region and one of the most promising Markets in the world. The demand for architects is growing annually. As the work field becomes more dynamic and complex, new technologies and systems are expected to spread rapidly to the construction sector [1, 2]. Many indicators show that architectural education in Saudi Arabia is not aligned with local demands and international accreditation standards. Identifying the gaps is essential in providing actionable recommendations to bridge this gap.

International educational organizations emphasize the importance of fostering the creative and critical thinking of undergraduate STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) students [3]. Students' prospects of success in the job market increase when their architectural abilities are developed. Nada argued that to produce autonomous and skilled architects, students must embrace a scientific and rational thinking style and creativity [4]. Achieving this requires designing architecture programs and utilizing contemporary teaching techniques emphasizing quality rather than quantity [5]. A study on the Australian graduates' capacity for innovation and entrepreneurship revealed a need for 'broad relational and problem-solving skills applicable across all disciplines' and suggested considering more internships, practical training, and projects outside the architecture program [6].

In The United States, a study identified the increasing need among graduates for critical thinking, problem-solving, entrepreneurship, technology familiarity, and professional ethics [3]. Expanding students' perspectives on urban planning, Nofal et al. suggested teaching building design disciplines inside an established framework of the urban fabric [7]. It should be noted that vital communication and critical thinking skills achieved during undergraduate study declined and translated into poorer employment outcomes [8]. More recently, researchers revealed that 45% of students view their undergraduate study as a step toward graduate study or work rather than a chance for learning or personal development [9].

A survey conducted by the national Australian employers revealed a gap in developing innovation, communication, collaboration, problem-solving, and work-related knowledge skills [10]. One of the most crucial components of architectural education is field training. To ensure the sustainability of architects' continuing education processes, Abu-Ghazaleh emphasizes the significance of pertinent authorities and governmental entities, such as the Saudi Council of Engineers, in the practical training of architecture students and in connecting rules and regulations to training [11]. The Association of American Colleges and Universities (AAC&U) employer report identified the gaps in problem-solving, critical thinking, effective teamwork, and capacity to apply knowledge and skills in real-world settings [12]. These arguments arguably lead to the importance of developing expertise in the chosen field of study but point to the quality of educational outcomes and the development of a broader set of skills that prepare graduates effectively for pursuing their careers ahead while fulfilling their society's needs.

Diversity in methodologies, instructional methods, and architectural generation ideas is essential, as noted by Shema and Al-Madhavji [13]. They recommended that educational curricula should be revised and updated regularly, focusing on

developing students' physical and mental hand abilities. This issue should be the question of curriculum design and educational approach. Professional degrees tend to have relatively fixed programs to prepare students for initial entry into the work field, with little room for broadening activities that prepare graduates to adapt to future changes.

Results of testing graduates' readiness for the labour market from professional and academic institutions alert the need for curriculum assessment and give the importance of this study. In 2022, results of a test conducted by the Saudi National Centre for Assessment in cooperation with the Saudi Council of Engineers revealed that the average performance of the examinees in the architecture test was 48% with a standard deviation of 11%, and the passing rate was 73% [14].

In 2024, the Saudi Education and Training Commission conducted an academic performance test for graduate students' readiness for the work field. The test covered 16 programs in 13 universities. Results revealed that the average of students' achievements in that state was only 42.17% [15]. These test results show that despite the ambitious 2030 Saudi Vision, architectural education lags in integrating professional practice, new construction and management technologies, and accreditation requirements.

Research Objectives: To pinpoint the specific areas where architectural education in Saudi Arabia falls short of meeting the demands of the local labour market and international accreditation organizations.

Research hypothesis: Graduates lack some skills and background knowledge to fulfil labour market requirements. Identifying these gaps is the basis for developing a better curriculum for architectural schools in KSA.

Research Methode: The study adopted a scientific qualitative approach supported by numerical data that was acquired and analysed to support the approach. Architectural departments were surveyed, and fourteen governmental and private schools' curriculums were collected, tabulated, and discussed. The selected programs represent private and governmental institutions and cover regions and main cities of the kingdom. They are all within the scope of architecture and architectural engineering.

The National Architectural Accrediting Board (NAAB) standards were adopted because they focus on architecture. Accreditation requirements were identified, categorized, and tabulated. The top international architectural firms operating in the Gulf region were ranked based on their revenue from architecture and their size. The skills and knowledge demanded by these firms for junior positions were obtained from the AIA Crear Centre. These skills and knowledge were identified, grouped, categorized, and tabulated.

The NAAB standards were selected as a benchmark for the knowledge and skills offered by architecture programs. A comparison is then made between the skills and knowledge graduates acquire in their schools and the requirements set by the international accrediting associations and the local labour market. The gaps are identified, and guidelines and recommendations for enhancing architectural curricula are concluded to align with the labour market requirements. Figure 1 illustrates the research methodology flowchart.

Fig. 1. Research methodology.

2. Local Construction and Consultation Market Characteristics

Saudi Arabia's ambitious Vision 2030 targets a thriving economy with an economic development agenda. This development program set targets for economic sectors. Several initiatives were developed to meet the set targets [16]. As one of these sectors, the construction sector plays a crucial role with more than 5,200 projects with an estimated value of USD 819 billion. These projects allow for increased growth of an already growing sector [17]. Based on this, the Saudi Arabian construction market is currently valued at USD 70 billion and is expected to grow at a Compound Annual Growth Rate of 4.5% (2023 - 2028), with a 67% share of the MENA construction market. This growth is driven by the Saudi Vision 2030 national development plan, which aims to diversify and privatize the Saudi economy [18].

The top ten contractors in Saudi Arabia are currently constructing projects worth USD 400 billion. According to MEED Projects, the Awarded projects in Saudi Arabia between 2021 and 2025 are expected to reach USD 569 billion. As of October 2022 report, USD 85 billion has been awarded across 2021 and 2022 [18].

The second pillar of the 2030 Saudi vision is a flourishing economy. The primary objective of this pillar is learning to work. This objective can be achieved through investing in education and training for future jobs. The outcomes of undergraduate education should align with work field requirements. University education should focus on entrepreneurship, innovation, and technology [19]. Saudi Arabia started to promote its cultural and religious assets to become the MENA tourism centre. This approach is expected to elevate the demand for construction. The hotel construction rate is anticipated to triple in 2023, with nearly 85 projects. In 2025 and beyond, it is likely to see at least 40 hotels representing 9,063 keys joining the market. A significant portion of the development wave is due to several mega projects in Makkah. With twenty-seven hotels, Makkah came third on the top Saudi city list, while Riyadh came first with 45 hotels totalling 9,302 rooms. Jeddah comes in second place with 33 projects delivering 7,148 rooms. Saudi Arabia is the leading regional architectural design consulting market in the MENA region. Saudi Arabia is considered the most prominent consulting

market in the MENA region, with an expansion of 18.2% in 2023, expected to reach \$3.2 billion by the end of 2024 [20].

The construction industry in Saudi Arabia employs around 23.7% of the total workforce; only 13.83% of these workers are locals. Statistics for the second quarter of 2024 revealed that the unemployment rate among Saudi nationals had reached 7.1%. Despite the non-local 3.39 million workers in the Saudi construction sector, the demand for a workforce will keep growing in the coming years [21]. Although 86.17% of the Saudi construction industry's workers are non-local, this sector can still reduce the unemployment rate by 4.7% for the second quarter of 2024. This figure is based on the distribution of the construction labour market [21, 22]. According to an employer survey, even though most unemployed Saudis are college graduates, they still require the necessary skills, qualifications, and knowledge to meet the job market's demand for Saudis with specific expertise. [21, 22].

3. Job Qualifications for Junior Jobs in International Architectural Firms

The top ten international architectural firms were identified based on their annual revenue from practicing architectural consultations and the number of employees. Figure 2 illustrates these firms and their revenues in millions, while Fig. 3 presents each firm's employees [23].

Fig. 2. Top ten architectural firms ranked based on revenue [24].

Fig. 3. Top ten architectural firms employees [24].

Qualifications for twenty junior architect positions were extracted and tabulated based on a survey covering the top ten international architectural firms practicing in the Gulf area. The required skills were categorized into five main categories: knowledge of different types of codes, knowledge of accessibility codes, graduation from an accredited program, awareness of the building standards, ability to prepare specifications, and a good command of utilizing computer tools within the job scope. An analysis of the requirements of these forms for Junior positions revealed that accreditation, registration, and research skills are the most required for such jobs. Figure 4 illustrates the five primary qualifications demanded for different Junior positions and the percentages of repetition for each one of these jobs [25].

Fig. 4. Main qualification sections for junior architect positions in international architectural firms [25].

The following sections discuss in detail each one of these qualifications:

3.1. Accreditation and registration

One could view the global accreditation process, which involves substantial equivalency and validation, as a tool for ongoing program development. Its substantial equivalency or validation is essential because it includes criteria designated for the professional practice of architecture. The same standards apply to accredited programs and prepare graduates for professional practice worldwide. To sum up, the RIBA validation or NAAB substantial equivalency accreditation is essential for promoting the competitiveness of architecture practice since it contains requirements for professional practice that will better equip graduates of recognized institutions for work in a global setting [25]. Attia revealed that global accreditation is a tool for continuous architecture curriculum development as it is considered the program validation since it contains architecture professional practice criteria. As the same criteria apply to all internationally accredited programs, graduates of these programs can compete in the global labour market [26].

The Job requirements posted on the AIA career centre revealed that 49% of firms required applicants to have graduated from an accredited school, and 37% of the Job ads required specific accreditation organizations. 51% of the Jobs required graduates to be registered with the local professional practicing organization. Moreover, 20% percent of the jobs require graduates to have specific certificates

like Riba, LEED, or PMP. Figure 5 illustrates different types of accreditation required for the junior architecture surveyed jobs.

Fig. 5. Percentage of accreditations required for the surveyed jobs [25].

3.2. Architectural knowledge

Based on the field of work and type of project, the required architectural knowledge varied, for example, Innovative design capabilities, construction documents, construction processes and materials, and building life cycle, as well as having a background in building envelope design, life safety, building systems, architectural details, and architectural culture and conservation. Detailed results of the percentage of each required architectural knowledge are presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Percentage of architectural knowledge [25].

3.3. Knowledge of codes and standards

Knowledge of the code was essential for half of the jobs studied. Extra knowledge of specifications preparation, standards analysis, and accessibility code implementation was required. Detailed results of the code background percentages are illustrated in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Percentage of required code knowledge [25].

3.4. Computer skills

As computer software has become an essential tool for any engineering practice, computer knowledge has become engineering literacy. Yimin Zhu et al. argued that stakeholders of the architecture education community must adopt curriculum development that promotes technology-enabled learning-centered environments and share this vision with professional associations and accreditation organizations [26].

Computer skills were the most requested skills qualifications with 30%. Revit proficiency and graphics skills (Photoshop, Illustrator, and InDesign) were required for almost all the jobs. Additional computer background was required for specific jobs, such as BIM advanced tools, construction administration tools, parametric design tools, and 3D rendering skills. Figure 8 shows the percentages of different computer skills.

Fig. 8. Percentage of required computer skills [25].

3.5. Soft skills

Since architecture is practiced within a team and involves managing relations with many stakeholders, job applicants must have many other skills. These skills include creativity, verbal and visual communication, management, collaboration, leadership, and more than one language, technical writing, and organizational skills. Figure 9 presents the percentage of these skills.

Fig. 9. Percentages of required soft skills [25].

4. Accreditation Requirements

Several national and international organizations offer quality assurance certificates for higher education programs. The National Centre for Academic Accreditation and Evaluation (NCAAA) is a well-recognized organization that certifies quality assurance education within the region. Its scope is general to quality in education rather than particular fields like architecture or engineering professional education. Some international institutions, such as the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET), focus on the quality of education in science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) programs. Agency for Study Programmes in Engineering, Informatics, Natural Sciences and Mathematics (ASSIN) accredits engineering and science programs, while others limit their scope to architectural programs, such as the NAAB, which evaluates only architecture programs. The current study considers the criteria of NAAB as a specialized organization. The NAAB International Certification conditions of 2020 include four main sections regarding the curriculum [27]. These sections are as follows:

4.1. Critical thinking and registration

Courses should enable graduates to develop diverse thinking skills, express ideas, and communicate them visually and verbally with others. These skills include Professional Communication Skills, Design Thinking Skills, Investigative Skills, Architectural Design Skills, Ordering Systems, History and Global Culture, and Cultural Diversity.

4.2. Integrated building practices, technical skills, and knowledge

Graduates should have technical knowledge of all design aspects, building systems, and materials. Areas of these skills are all needed for pre-design activities, analysing and dealing with site conditions, applying codes and regulations, making technical documents, applying basic principles of structural systems, studying environmental conditions and designing for different climatic zones, selecting finishing interior and exterior materials, considering different systems requirements, and estimating building life-cycle costs.

4.3. Integrated architectural solutions

Graduates could develop integrated designs that consider a wide range of influencing aspects. To achieve such abilities, the curriculum should include

applied research methods and practices, design process and decision-making, design criticism, and Integrative Design.

4.4. Professional practice

Graduates must understand business principles, including management, advocacy, and legal aspects of professional practice. Therefore, the curriculum should include the topics of stakeholders' roles in architecture practice, project management, business practice, legal responsibilities, and professional conduct.

4.5. Basic architectural and engineering courses

In addition to the Four categories and their corresponding topics that are illustrated in Fig. 10, It is required that each professional program should include architectural content courses, and the curriculum must include a course of study that covers 30% of the total number of credits. Curriculums should contain courses outside architectural general studies to address the institute's mission. Programs' curriculums are required to allow students to develop their minors and areas of concentration through elective courses. The research's primary goal is to show the specific areas where architectural education in Saudi Arabia falls short of meeting the demands of the local labour market.

Fig. 10. Skills required by NAAB accreditation of architectural programs [28].

5. Architecture Education Programs

The Saudi Ministry of Education site shows that Saudi Arabia has forty-two universities [29, 30]. Twenty-nine educational institutions are governmental, while the rest are private. As illustrated in Fig. 11, Twenty-four institutions have architectural programs divided equally between the governmental and private institutions. Four of these twenty-four programs have equivalent accreditation from NAAB: Dar Al-Uloum, Effat, King Saud, and Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal. On the other hand, the King Fahd program is accredited by the ABET, the Prince Sultan program by NCAAE, and the Umm Al-Qura Program by ASIIN [28, 31-33].

Fig. 11. Governmental and private education [29, 30].

5.1. Case study selection criteria

Case studies were selected based on the following criteria:

- Represent private and governmental universities.
- Distributed in the main cities of Saudi Arabia.
- Curriculum details are available online.
- Programs within architecture and architectural engineering scope.

Fourteen programs were selected based on the previous criteria. King Abdulaziz, Umm Al Qura, Imam Abdulrahman, Najaran, Al Qasim, and Al Baha were selected as case studies for governmental programs. Effat, Dar El-Hekma, Sultan, Mohamed bin Fahd, Dar-Alulom, Al-Majmaah, and Al Yamamah programs were selected as private program case studies.

5.2. Programs' credits

Figure 12 compares the credit hours of the fourteen case study programs. Data from the fourteen Saudi institutions showed consistency in the total number of credits, with an average total of 161 credits and 30 standard deviations (Developed by the author). Only three exceptions: Umm Al Qura University adopted a semester system with 255 credits [34]. This large number of credits fulfils the requirements of the ASSIN accrediting organization and the university's general subject requirements. Najran has the lowest number of credits, 135 [35], and Prince Sultan University has 138 [36].

Fig. 2. Credit hours of the fourteen studied architecture programs.

5.3. Curriculums' topics

After reviewing the curriculums' contents, offered topics were grouped into the fourteen categories as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Categories of studied programs.

Categories	
Humanities	Basic Engineering
Basic Architecture	Building Science
Research Skills & knowledge	Design skills and knowledge
Environment	Building structure
Building Construction	History and Theories
Computer Applications	Professional Skills
Urban & Site Planning	Electives

The total credits of each category in the studied programs are presented in Table 2. It could be noticed that basic sciences have more credit hours in institutions with architectural engineering programs like Najran, Al Faisal, and King Abdulaziz universities. It should also be noted that some programs do not have dedicated courses for research, computer applications, professional practice, or environmental studies; these topics are covered in other subjects but are still partially covered.

Table 2. Total credits of each category in the studied programs.

Program Scope	Governmental Programs								Private Programs					
	Basic Engineering	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture I Engineering	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Architecture	Design & Architectur	Architecture
Organization	Najran	Qasim	Al baha	Umm AlQura	King Abdulaziz	Imam Abdulrahman	Al Faisal	Al Majmaah	Al Yamamah	Effat university	Dar Alulom	Sultan	Dar Elhakma	Mohamad Bin Fahd
Humanities	12	17	12	30	26	21	17	21	13	25	21	14	11	12
Basic Sciences	32	2	14	4	24	9	30	12	9	12	12	4	6	11
Creativity	9	11	15	15	9	4	3	11	8	9	22	15	12	13
Environmental Studies	4	4	3	14	6	9	6	0	8	9	4	6	0	15
History & Theories	6	14	7	10	8	14	3	8	10	6	15	10	12	12
Computer Applications	4	9	7	10	11	7	0	0	4	12	4	6	14	10
Building Science	9	2	7	2	2	0	13	7	6	6	5	0	6	3
Built Environment	4	6	12	20	6	8	3	9	8	3	9	10	6	6
Construction Documents	14	18	21	38	8	9	22	14	15	12	12	15	9	9
Civil Studies	18	8	15	10	0	14	12	6	8	6	13	6	9	9
Research	2	2	5	2	2	3	4	0	3	5	0	2	0	6
Design Studios	19	35	35	74	40	55	6	49	47	46	39	31	50	40
Elective Courses	0	23	6	16	16	12	9	10	8	12	12	9	16	6
Professional Practice	2	2	3	10	2	5	0	11	10	0	4	13	11	11
	135	153	162	255	160	170	128	158	157	163	172	141	162	163

The distribution of the studied program credits on the main offered topics is calculated and illustrated in Fig. 13 [37-42]. It can be noted from Fig. 13 that the average credits for basic science and general categories were 42, with Dar Al-Uloom University having a maximum of 55 credits [46] and Dar EL-Hikma having

the lowest of 29 hours [45]. Computer courses allow students to express their ideas and communicate with others visually. Ranged from four to fourteen credits. Built environment courses with a big gap between twenty and three credits. Building construction had an average of 15.4 credits, ranging between eight credits at El-Imam University and thirty-eight credits at Umm Al-Qura University [34, 46]. The architectural design courses averaged 40.4 credits, with at least six credits at Al-Faisal University [42] and seventy-four credits at Umm Al Qura University [34]. The average credit for elective courses that allow students to develop areas of concentration was 11.1, with a maximum of 23 credits at Al Qasim University [47] and no elective courses at all at Najran University [48]. Environmental Studies required for accreditation organizations and job demands were found to have an average of 6.3 credits, ranging between three Dar Al-Uloum and fourteen hours at Prince Mohamed Bin-Fahd [49].

Fig. 13. Credit hours distribution of the main categories of the curriculum of the studied programs.

6. Results and Discussion

6.1. Comparison of curriculum and accreditation requirements

Although every program is built based on its academic institution's mission to serve its local community, the minimum knowledge and skills defined by the accrediting association should be maintained to ensure the competitiveness of the graduates in the globalization era. The results of comparing the tabulated categories of subjects in the fourteen surveyed curriculums and the requirements of the NAAB as an architectural accreditation organization are shown in Fig. 14.

The figure also shows the following: the accreditation required design skills such as developing innovative concepts, integrative design, and analysing alternatives, which are already the core of all the studied curriculums. Codes, regulations, and architectural standards are covered well in the studied programs. The humanity category is covered with different topics and credits percent between programs based on the mission and objectives of the institution. Surveying, structural analysis, and materials are also covered with different credit percentages

in the curriculums according to each program scope. Basics of computer applications are given to students. Professional practicing skills are covered through different courses, including internships and summer training. Research skills are covered in dedicated courses and throughout the other curriculum topics. Building systems and construction documents are also covered in all the studied curricula with different percentages based on the nature and scope of the program.

Comparing the topics offered to the accreditation organization's requirements revealed that most programs studied did not meet the 30% ratio of basic sciences. Moreover, the following sub-topics in the curriculums are not required by the accreditation organizations:

- Basic Architectural Sciences: Architectural models, colour theory, freehand drawing, descriptive geometry, shades & perspective.
- Building Construction: Reinforced concrete, soil mechanics, surveying.
- Professional Skills: Registration, Personal development, leadership & teamwork, voluntary service.
- Computer Applications: Digital fabrication and prototyping, BIM tools, contracts and liability for buildings and construction, Revit proficiency.

On the other hand, some missing categories and topics must be integrated with the curriculums to fulfil international accreditation requirements, like business practice and its sub-topics: Marketing, financial management, and business planning. Specialized advanced topics like BIM, LEED building accreditation, and primavera must be considered elective courses. The financial considerations category and its sub-topics, including building life cycle cost, construction cost estimation, and operational cost, are required by the accrediting international organization to be embedded within curriculums. In addition to these categories, some sub-topics are either founded as electives or embedded within other courses or have very few credit hours, like thinking skills, criticism, building envelope analysis, problem-solving, construction and finishing materials, and construction administration.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the main categories offered by architectural programs and the requested categories in accreditation organizations.

6.2. Comparison of curriculum and labour market requirements

Figure 15 shows a Sanky chart that links the categories and sub-topics the studied

educational programs offer to the knowledge and skills demanded by the junior architects' jobs. The figure shows that international firms do not directly require many courses offered in the studied curriculums, but these courses constitute the basic knowledge for practicing engineering and architecture.

On the other hand, topics like business planning, materials performance, life safety principles, material environmental impact, energy envelope energy performance, and stakeholders in architecture are required for many junior jobs that were surveyed during this study. Preparation for specialized professional exams like LEED and PMP were also missing from curriculums. Moreover, it can be noticed from the study plans that most of the programs offer professional practice courses in the final semester. The following categories and sub-topics were demanded for junior architect jobs. Despite some of these topics already being covered in elective courses, this means that some graduates would miss them. It is strongly recommended for these topics to be taught through dedicated compulsory courses rather than electives.

- Business practices: Cost estimation, financial management, Business planning, Operational costs, and stakeholders in Architecture.
- Professional Skills: Analytical thinking, design criticism, problem-solving, and professional registration.
- Building Construction: Construction and Finishing materials, Building components & assemblies, Materials Performance, Material environmental impact and reuse, principles of local life-safety, Integrated decisions across multiple systems, Integrative Design, and Envelope Energy Performance, durability
- Software Certification: 3D Modelling & Rendering tools, BIM tools, Enscape, and management software.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the main categories offered by programs and the requested knowledge categories by the labour market.

6.3. Gap identification in academic curriculum

Figure 16 summarises the results of comparing the categories and sub-topics offered by the surveyed educational programs, the accreditation requirements, and the required

skills for labour market jobs. As illustrated in the figure, there is a mismatch between the requirements of the academic accreditation organizations and the required skills for junior architecture jobs. Academic accreditation organizations do not require topics like specialized computer software and preparation courses for certification in advanced specialties like environmental accreditation systems, project management certification, management software, or BIM tools, but the surveyed jobs demand it. Based on this, it is recommended that enhancing these categories and sub-topics within the curriculums and offering more courses to cover these subtopics would support graduates in pursuing their professional paths. The comparison showed that a balance in the categories and the topics credits should be maintained to match the requirements of the international accreditation organizations.

The professional practice category and its sub-topics are the basis for any success in the after-graduation practice. Accreditation organizations require the least featured topics: ethical practice, local regulations, service contracts, and risk management [50]. At the same time, the job market requirements were organizational skills, leadership, collaboration, and administrative skills. The study of professional practice within the studied programs documented a disproportional orientation towards traditional professional practice. In a similar study, a survey of graduates in Pennsylvania

The United States revealed that practitioners and recent graduates still feel unprepared for the profession after graduation. It is recommended that the "Professional Practice" courses to be more inclusive by adding more coursework or changing the current course to give students the necessary skills [51]. A study in Turkey revealed that professional practice courses are included in the final semester's thirty-seven architecture programs with ECTS credits ranging between 6 and 12 out of 240 ECTS credits. The most frequently covered sub-topic is Development Law and Legislation.

Fig. 5. Labour demanded missing skills from the curriculums and the accreditation requirements.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper investigated the courses offered by a study of fourteen architecture programs and compared them with the job requirements of junior architecture jobs in ten of the most prominent architectural international firms practicing within the Gulf area. The

comparison included the guidelines for international accreditation organizations.

Results show that some programs are not aligned with accreditation organization requirements in sub-topics and the ECTS credits of the courses. The imbalance in the contact hours and credits between program categories resulted in a lack of graduates' knowledge in topics like building construction, software utilization, integrative design, and professional practice requirements. Many required personal skills like creativity, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Additionally, professional skills and knowledge like integrative design, criticism, marketing, finance management, business planning, leadership, organization, cost estimation, and value engineering did not have clear dedicated courses in the discussed program's curriculum. On the other hand, some programs have courses not required by the architectural labour market or the accreditation organization, such as physical education, architectural models, soil mechanics, steel design, and surveying and fabrication.

Limitations: Architecture education has three pillars: student, teacher, and curriculum. This study is concerned with the curriculum. The research considered only programs with published detailed curricula online. The study was built on creating categories of topics that lead to acquiring specific knowledge and skills. Comparing these categories with the knowledge and skills required by both NAAB and professional junior Job skills leads to identifying the gaps in knowledge needed to enhance the graduates' competitiveness. No learning outcomes of the programs were investigated.

Future work: This research opens the door for several studies in the field. Further investigations could cover architecture schools of the MENA region. An evaluation of graduates' performance in different work areas of the market through surveying the employers would help identify the required modifications to the outcomes of sample programs. Moreover, evaluating the impact of professional training and internships on the graduates' performance in the labour market would help enhance the skills acquired from these courses.

Recommendations for Curriculum Development:

- Program development committees should survey local and international firms to increase their graduates' competitiveness and determine their requirements for junior architectural positions.
- The program management committee should design and implement a work plan to include missing topics within the existing courses to bridge the gap with the defined international professional practice requirements.
- The Ministry of Education invites professional associations, practicing firms, local and international accreditation organizations, and architecture programs' developing teams to a conference to define the minimum requirement for each program to meet the needs of international accreditation and the labour market.
- The requirements of local and international professional accreditation organizations specialized in architecture must be investigated, extracted, and tabulated. Their categories and sub-topics must be considered as the minimum base of the curriculum topics.
- Work with Architecture Professional Associations to update and align programs' learning outcomes with the labour market requirements.
- Cooperate with Architecture Professional Associations to offer continuous learning programs for graduate architects.

- A balance must be maintained between the organization's orientation and the minimum required topics to prepare graduates to compete globally.
- Details of construction and finishing materials must be introduced to students in terms of cost, durability, physical characteristics, and environmental impact.
- Professional practice should be introduced in more than one course to cover all the required practicing skills required by Junior jobs employees.

Having elective courses from inside and outside the program is essential in preparing graduates to pursue their minor specialization and fit the available jobs in the market.

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